

A Corpus Based Study of Anglicism: Neologism in Urdu Through Phono-Semantic Matching

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Abstract

The study finds impact of Anglicism as a result of language contact and technological advancement in the Urdu newspaper 'The Daily Jang'. Language contact allows speakers to transfer new words from source language to target language. Phono semantic matching words are borrowed neologisms which retain their approximate sound and meaning. The neologism expressions such as words having Phono-Semantic Matching (PSM) do not at once get acceptance in monolingual dictionaries of Urdu. The morphological system of Urdu allows certain types of inflections to PSM words in the target language. This study explores such data in order to create a corpus for bilingual dictionary of Urdu using Zuckerman's model (2003) for PSM. Data is collected from the Daily Jang newspaper since September 2021 to November 2021. Types of PSM included for analytical categories are PSM through preexistent form, Incestuous PSM by semantic shifting and PSM introducing a new form and partial PSM. The results show that the most productive PSM found in Urdu neologisms is introducing a new form and partial PSM.

Keywords: Neologism, Phono-Semantic Matching (PSM), Urdu Morphology

1. Introduction

In the era of technological and cultural modifications every living being continues to coin new notions. The entanglement of life in the progress of substantial and divine native or foreign cultural products is an enduring phenomenon. Therefore, the need of new word formation is intensely required in more advanced cultural and technological transformation since the 18th century (Rosenhouse & Kowner 2008).

The internet and the advent of social media give rise to mixing of languages. The predominant impact of English language in non-academic discourses specifically cause linguistic intrusion such as borrowing. Borrowing is an umbrella term for not only single words, but it also includes phenomena such as hybridization and phono semantic matching (PSM). The influence of English language on any other recipient language is called Anglicism, which consequently introduces newly coined expressions into the target language. The contact of two languages resulting in any semantic change of a word which already exists in the recipient language, is also a domain of neologism. Hence, in Anglicization of Urdu, the effects of linguistics norms of English are included as a part of neologism. Semantic Anglicism focuses on the output instead of the structure, which is not independent of the output (Picone, M.D 1996). Similarly, the effect of Anglicism on French language, manifests itself by showing English structural influence on French words. Hence, a framework of identifying neologism must incorporate both semantic and structural influence of English on other languages.

1.1. Neologism

Neologism means the inclusion of any newly coined word, borrowed word, part of a word or new sound or meaning given to an existing word of a recipient language (Picone, 1996). Mostovy (1993) defines neologism as a linguistic unit which adds a new notion to a word. A more inclusive definition of neologism given by Akhmanova (2007, p.265) in the dictionary of linguistics terms includes its two types. The first definition constitutes a word or phrase as neologism. The second part states that it is a new word which is dissociated nationally and supposed as inferior discourse styles (Levchenko, 2010, p. 55). Therefore, for the inclusion of a word in a dictionary it has to occur frequently in a text. (Fischer, 1998.p.3). In other words, "Neologisms are like casting show winners" (Kerremans, 2016. p.14). Lexicographers consider those words as novel words which have not yet found their place in English dictionaries. Algeo (1991, p. 4) believes that any word or morpheme not documented in any general dictionary is said to be new. Yartseva proposes that "neologisms are words, word meanings or collocations that appeared in a certain period in a language or that once use in a text or speech act" (p.279). Lexicogenes is a term interchangeably used for neological and lexical productivity (Tournier 1985, 1991, Picone, (1996).

According to Cook (2010, p.12) lexicogenes is in a particular language involves three functions; coinage of new constructions, labelling new meaning to existing form of word, and forming more categories. The example of first kind of lexicogenes is given as webisode for web episode. The second category is explained with the words coming from Middle Ages for instance "circuit and digital" into the computer age. The third kind is exemplified by the formation of verb "to google" from noun Google (Ahmed, 2000).

The Dutch linguist M. Janssen points out five parameters for any word to be a neologism. This includes psychological, lexicographic, exclusive, and diachronic definitions. For a language community, a newly perceived word is new, for

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a lexicographer the new word must not already be included in the dictionary, and the word should not be in pre-determined exclusion lexicon. According to diachronic definition, a new word appearing in a general language text which was not found before in the language is neologism (Zabotkina, 2010, p.12). Moreover, in terms of reference corpora, any word appearing in common language is a neologism (ibid). Lastly, Zabotkina states “extended lexicographic diachronic definition” which states that word not found in morphological data bases and those which are derived from dictionaries can be neologism.

One of the major reason of neologism is the lesser capacity of conventional words to express as compared to borrowed words. The second reason is that; evolving languages frequently expand their lexicons. Third reason is technological advancement, which shows adaptive nature of a language that is equipped with the modern tools of advanced technology. Fourth according to cognitive linguistics, language is not only a communicative contrivance, but it also organises perception about the word and forms a language vocabulary intelligible. Hence, new words help to identify the popular culture (Danis Jennet, 2018).

A number of changes can be observed as a result of close contact of languages. One of these changes is borrowing (Thomason and Kaufman 1988, p. 66). For example, English has adapted many cultural substances such as pizza, sauerkraut, tortilla and sushi from Italian, German, Mexican Spanish and Japanese respectively.

For instance, American English has assimilated a number of immigrant groups' cultural practices, such as kosher from Yiddish, pizza from Italy, sauerkraut from Germany, tortilla from Mexican Spanish, sushi from Japan, and so on. On the other hand, many studies of extensive borrowing, the outcome of intensive contact, assume that the necessary starting point is a subset of all native speakers of the recipient variety who are also reasonably proficient and possibly equally skilled in the donor, who acts as a kind of channel for the diffusion of lexical items and other qualities of the donor language (Thomason and Kaufman 1988: 66). Among others, Grosjean (1982) makes a distinction between (a) speech borrowing, which occurs when a speaker spontaneously adopts a form from another language within an utterance (possibly adapting it in varying degrees phonologically and morphologically), and (b), language borrowing, which occurs when words from one language have been borrowed by another and used by monolingual speakers of that recipient language.

2. Literature Review

Through changing some foreign language characteristics of the borrowed words or expressions, according to the phonetic and semantic features native language a new word is incorporated which is also sometimes called camouflaged borrowing. This outcome of language contact is observed by Zuckermann (2000) Found in Israeli Hebrew or Modern Hebrew, Finish, Turkish and Icelandic from which objectionable borrowed words were replaced by language planners. Moreover, languages having phonologographic script such as Kangi of Japanese and Chinese also have phonosemantic features. PSM contributes in Icelandic in the process of new word formation. In the Icelandic language, PSM is classified in two main categories; first PSM through creation of the new form and second BSM PSM through and existing form (Sapir-Zuckermann,2008, p.19). Sapir (2003, pp.63-64) identifies the basis of new word formation through PSM in any language in the following ways. First is the exnihilo in which it is denoted with Zero source which means lexemes are not based on pre-existing lexemes. Second category is exsono which means sound source that provides the base for a new word form created by the reproduction of sounds. The third category is exexterno which means that the new term is formed by the foreign vocabulary.

According to Sapir reproduction is a phenomenon in which one or more base forms keep their characteristics and positions in a vocabulary system, but they are imitated to create new word (2003, p. 51). It demonstrates that in the PSM process instead of directly borrowing words from another language, the words are replicated as ex-externo from the source or foreign language. Likewise, in exinterno, a newly created word can be restructured through the process of inflection or compounding to create new forms from native language.

In the evolution of a language foreign and native source of vocabulary are productive in initial phases, which give rise to zero and sound sources. The vocabulary source is either separated or interrelated in different ways. Calquing is one of the word formation processes which bifurcates the source, for instance a form of word in exinterno is created by reducing a form in exinterno (ibid). For example, in the Icelandic language a form *fjarkennsla* is created by calquing into English collocating word ‘distance teaching’ whereas *fjar* means distance and *kennsla* teaching. Hence, to PSM word formation occurs by combining exexterno senses and phonemes and matching them with their equivalent sense and phonemes in exexterno element (Sapir& Zuckermann 2008, p.20). (paraphrased)

The phenomenon of PSM can be further clarified by an Icelandic word *eyðni* (AIDS) is phono-semantically matched with an English acronym AIDS. The word *eyðni* comprises of Icelandic *eyða* ‘to destroy’ and the suffix *ni*. The word is reproduced by bifurcation. As described above PSM can be referred to ex externo or ex interno concurrently because of ex externo’s phonetic and semantic matching with prior indigenous ex interno form. Therefore, PSM may be

identified as a neologism that conserves meaning and fairly accurate sound of the imitated word in the source language (SL) with the support of preexistent target language (TL) components.

y is phonetically similar to x

b is similar to a

y' is based on y

a' is based on a

Figure 1: The following figure illustrates the process of PSM generally

Phono-Semantic Matching of *AIDS* in Icelandic adapted from Sapir, Y., Zuckermann, G. (2008). 'Icelandic: Phonosemantic Matching', in Judith Rosenhouse and Rotem Kowner (eds), *Globally Speaking: Motives for Adopting English Vocabulary in Other Languages*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.

The following figure illustrates the process of PSM in Icelandic word *eyðni* 'AIDS':

Figure 2: Phono-Semantic Matching of AIDS in Icelandic

Phono-Semantic Matching of *AIDS* in Icelandic adapted from Sapir, Y., Zuckermann, G. 2008. 'Icelandic: Phonosemantic Matching', in Judith Rosenhouse and Rotem Kowner (eds), *Globally Speaking: Motives for Adopting English Vocabulary in Other Languages*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.

The lack of analytical investigation for this type of lexical improvement found in various languages was highlighted by Zukermann & Sapir (2008, p. 29). This kind of lexical improvement, according to Zukermann & Sapir (2008, p. 29), is common but not analytically studied. For instance, Sivan (1963: 37–38) mentions this process just once in three lines of his book *Patterns and Trends of Linguistic Innovations in Modern Hebrew*. PSM is referred to as *calques phonétiques* by Heyd (1954, p. 90), *emprunt-calembour* by Hagège (1986, p. 257), and *phonetic transposition* by Toury (1990).

Li (1990) suggests phonetic translation in addition to semantic translation for Modern Standard Chinese (MSC). Hansell defends semanticized loan (1989) and semanticized transcription. In Taiwanese Mandarin, ‘yinzhongy’ is defined as “sound + middle + have + meaning” or ‘transcript’ in which the meaning lies within the sound” by Yao (1992). (2003) Zukermann Additionally, it's possible that PSM won't succeed in attracting the attention of specialists in Icelandic word formation. PSM is not included in the traditional classification of borrowing, but Zuckerman & Sapir (2008, p. 30) believe it to be a distinct phenomenon caused by foreign and alternative lexemes or morphemes. For lexicology, historical comparative linguistics, sociolinguistics, and cultural studies, the realization of PSM has ramifications (ibid).

Similar to this, a significant study on the morphology of loan words from Arabic, Persian, and English in Urdu was conducted by Mangrio (2016, p. 158). However, the current study develops a corpus and analyzes specific Urdu newspaper data. Singh (2004, p. 244) advocates studying PSM hybrids in Hindi. Urdu has basic semitic morphological characteristics that are shared by Arabic, Persian, Sanskrit, and more recently English due to its distinct historical and sociolinguistic circumstances, making it primarily productive and useful.

One of the main concerns of the study was the need to examine PSM in Urdu. For instance, the English word "parliament" first appeared in print on January 20, 1974 in *Roznama Jang*, p.6 as a hybridized Urdu word called "parlimani," where the English suffix "ent" was changed to the Urdu suffix "ni." Due to the fact that it hides the influence of the source language from speakers of the target language and confirms lexicographic acceptability by reusing native roots and words, this multi-sourced neologization enriches the vocabulary of both language learners and native speakers (Zuckermann, 2004, p. 281). It is referred to as disguised hybridity by Zukermann (ibid).

2.1. Objectives

- To investigate influence of Anglicism on Urdu PSM words
- To find new expressions in PSM formation

3. Methodology

In this work, Zukerman's phonosemantic matching theory is used. Modern written Urdu, like many other languages of the world, has adopted a remarkable hybrid feature of English in a gradual process of anglicization (Nevalainen,1999, p. 1475). An alternative term for this process is, used interchangeably as Anglicization, Westernization, and Europeanization. On the other hand, the influence of Urdu on English is considered Urduization. This includes duplication, coinage, hybridization, etc. The Urdu corpus helps researchers carry out the classification process. Hybrid features can be found by comparing the original Urdu and English words side-by-side. Urdu tends to absorb English vocabulary and is used mainly in the form of loanwords. Similarly, we know that English loanwords acquired Urdu linguistic features in the process of phonological matching and hybridization.

Figure 3. Theoretical Framework

Zuckermann's (2003) adapted model for Categorization of Phono-Semantic Matching in Urdu

The empirical approach to investigating naturally occurring language is different from the rational approach because the former is based on systematic observations of language, while the latter is based on cognizant reflective rulings

(Neumann and Hansen-Schirra, 2012, p21). Additionally, reliability and validity are two important features of empirical research. This study helps to revitalize Urdu by providing a parallel corpus (McEnery & Wilson 2001, p.8).

3.1. Data Collection

The data is collected from Urdu newspaper ‘The Daily Jang’. For the current study, Sunday newspapers from September 2021 to November 2021 are analyzed. There is no software for the detection of PSM, so data will be analyzed manually using Urdu Lughat (The Ministry of Information Technology the Government of Pakistan, 2006) and online Oxford Learner’s Dictionary.

4. Data Analysis

The collected data is organized in three categories identified by Zuckermann (2008). The first category is PSM pre-existent form, the second is Incestuous PSM by Semantic Shifting and the third is PSM Introducing a New form & Partial PSM.

4.1. PSM pre-existent form

In this type, the PSM words are already found in Urdu from Persian.

Table.1. Shows PSM pre-existent form

Sr.no.	PSM word with IPA	Urdu Script	English Translation	Parallel Urdu Corpora
1.	Afsar / əfsər /	افسر	Officer	سردار، حاکم سربراہ
2.	Jaam / ja: m /	جام	Jam	ساغر

4.1.1. Afsar / əfsər / افسر

The word ‘afsar’ came from English language word officer, with an Arabic transcript. It is used in Urdu with its original meaning hence, there is no semantic shift. It is used in Urdu as a noun and first it was introduced in the year 1838 in the book “Gulzar e Naseem”. With the change from officer to ‘Afsar’ افسر the vowel sounds are changed. Hence, it is a camouflaged borrowing which makes the new word appear as if it is the part of target language’s sound system. Furthermore, with Urdu inflection this word takes pluralized form ‘Afsaroun’ افسروں and ‘Afsaran’ افسران which show the adaptive behavior of Urdu morphology.

4.1.2. Jaam / ja: m / [جام]

The word ‘jaam’ has Persian origin and it is first used in Urdu language in 1611 Kulyaat e Quli Qutub Shah and it is used as a noun. Later, in 1955 the word ‘jam’ is used as ‘ism e kafiyaat’ (اسم کیفیت) which means a noun that shows the condition of something. Here it means to stop or hindrance of some function. It falls in between first and second category. However, here is a phonetic difference of pronunciation between English word ‘jam’ and Persian origin word ‘jaam’(جام).

4.2. Incestuous PSM by semantic shifting

The following words have changed their meaning while adapting from English.

Table 2. Shows Incestuous PSM by semantic shifting

Sr.no.	PSM word with IPA	Urdu Script	Parallel Urdu Corpora	English Translation	Phono-Semantic change in Urdu
1.	Shaaper / ʃɑ: pɪ /	شاپر	تھیلا	Shopping bag	Shopper means a person who shops
2.	Jaam / ja: m /	جام	رکاوٹ	Obstacle	Jam is used for goblet or glass

4.2.1. Shaaper [شاپر]

English word shopper is inexterno. It is derived by inflecting the word shop with the bound morpheme – er. Shopper means the person who buys. But in Urdu speakers consider the word shaaper as a shopping bag. This is an instance of incestuous PSM by semantic shifting. The second word is Jaam which is semantically changed in Urdu and used for glass or goblet. The word jam is already explained above.

4.3. PSM Introducing a New form & Partial PSM

Twenty PSM words are found in the third category. The changes occurred from source to target language are presented in International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA).

Table 3: Represents PSM Introducing a New form & Partial PSM

Sr.no.	Urdu Words	IPA	Urdu Script	Parallel Urdu Corpora	English Translation
1.	Parlیمان	/par:ləman/	پارلیمان	مقننہ، مجلس شوریٰ	Parliament
2.	Parlیمانی	/par:ləmani/	پارلیمانی	تمثیلی	Parliamentary
3.	Daramai	/dra:mai/	ڈرامائی	تمثیلی	Dramatic
4.	Pistaul	/pistaul/	پستول	No substitute	Pistol
5.	Restoraan	/resturan/	رستوران	طعام خانہ	Restaurant
6.	Takneek	/tekni:k/	تکنیک	اصول فن کاری گری	Technique
7.	Taknieeki	/tekni:ki/	تکنیکی	فنی	Technical
8.	Bertania	/bartaniya/	برطانیہ	No substitute	Britain
9.	Brtanwi	/bartanvi/	برطانوی	No substitute	British
10.	Fraadia	/fradiya/	فراڈیا	دھوکہ باز	Fraudulent
11.	Kaapy	/kapi/	کاپی	چلڈ نسخہ نقل	Copy
12.	Fraanzik	/franzik/	فرانزک	No substitute	Forensic
13.	Haspatal	/haspatal/	ہسپتال	تفا خانہ	Hospital
14.	Ziabeetus	/ziəbitas/	ذیابیطس	No substitute	Diabetes
15.	Falsafa	/falsəfa/	فلسفہ	جگہت دانائی تفکر	Philosophy
16.	Falsafi	/falsəfi/	فلسفی	حکیم دانا مفکر مُنبر مُحَقِّق	Philosopher
17.	Garaaj	/geraʒ/	گیراج	No substitute	Garage
18.	Bum	/bam/	بم	گولے بارود تیزاب اور مہلک اپنی اسلحہ سے بہرا ہوا گولا	Bomb
19.	Godam	/gədam/	گودام	بازخانہ	Godown
20.	Patloon	/patlu:n/	پتلون	No substitute	Pantaloom

The following examples included in the third category of PSM exhibit partial changes of sound whereas the meaning remains intact.

4.3.1. Parlیمان / pa: rli: ma: n / پارلیمان

The word parlیمان پارلیمان is derived from the English word parliament. It was used in 1947 in “Mazameen e Farhat” by Mirza Farhatullah Baig. Its Urdu equivalent is ‘Majlis e shoorah’ (مجلس شوریٰ) which is not used in the newspaper. Rather, the word parliament is used after dropping its suffix –ment and adding Urdu suffix –aan اُن. /ā:/ .

4.3.2. Parlیمانی / pa: rli: ma: ni: / [پارلیمانی]

The word parlیمان is an adjective and is derived from English adjectives “parliamentary”. The English suffix –ary is replaced by Urdu suffix –aan, /ā:/ which is used to make adjectives in Urdu.

4.3.3. Takneek / tekni: k / تکنیک

The English word technique came from French and Latin technichus and also from Greek technikkos. When it comes to Urdu the /t/ sound changes into Urdu ʒa sound and PSM word tekneek is formed. The derivational form of tekneek is an adjective tekneeki تکنیکی.

4.3.4. Tekneeki / tekni: ki / تکنیکی

The English word technical is transformed into tekneeki in Urdu by the removal of English suffix –al and by the addition of Urdu suffix –ee یے. Again the initial sound of /t/ is changed into Urdu /ʒa/ ڄا. However, it retains the approximate sound and meaning of original word technique.

4.3.5. Britain / bɑr ʒa: ni: a: / برطانیہ

The word Britain came from English Breoton and from Latin Brittones. The word has changed the form from French Bretagne and from Latin Brit (t) annia. This term acquired historical value in the middle of 16th century when England and Scotland were supposed to be united. In Urdu Britain comes from برطان changes into Bertania برطانیہ with the addition of Urdu suffix –iya یہ and used as a noun.

4.3.6. Bertanwi / Barʒa: nwi: / برطانوی

Another derivation of bertitan in Urdu is bertanwi which is formed by the Urdu suffix –wi وی. It is first used in 1887 in muqadus naznein as an adjective in Urdu its Urdu equivalent is British. It is partially phonosomentic and approximate sound and meaning. The /t/ sound of britan is Urdu twa /t/ sound.

4.3.7. Fraadia / fra: qi: ja: / فراڈیا

In English this non-fraud came from old French word Fraude and Latin Fraus. In Urdu dictionary this word exists with its derivation such as fraadia and Fraadi فراڈی are found in Urdu newspaper. Hence –ie and - I ya suffixes are added to form new PSM adjectives while it's English equivalent is fraudulent with the addition of suffix - ulent to the route fraud.

4.3.8. Franzik / fəra: nzik / [فرانزک]

The English adjective forensic came from Latin word (forensic) which in the middle of 17th century “in open court, public quotation “something out of the doors. OED in Urdu newspapers this adjective occur PSM word. Though it is not documented in Urdu dictionary. Initial syllable is changed from /foren/ to Fran. It forms a consonant cluster at the beginning. The Final syllable is almost same which is “Zik” زک.

4.3.9. Haspatal /Aspatal اسپتال/ہسپتال

It came into Middle English via old French from Medieval Latin hospital, which means host or guest.

It came into Middle English via old French from Medieval Latin hospital, meaning host, guest. Verbally it was used with the British arrival but it is found in the written form in 1869. The initial phoneme / h / is changed into /a/ while comes into Urdu language. The vowel /ɒ/ is omitted and /a/ is joined with /s/. Then / ɪ / is deleted and changed into /ə/ and the new PSM is created from /'hɒspɪtl / that is, aspataal /Aspətal /. With the addition of suffix-oun it becomes plural, aspataaloun /Aspətalɔ:/.

4.3.10. Ziabeetus / zɪ:bi: tʌs / [ذیابیطس]

It came in English in middle 16th century via Latin from Greek ‘diabainein’ which means ‘go through’. After considerable changes in its sound it came into Urdu from English. It first appeared in written form in 1924 in (Insha e Bashir) (Urdu Lughat, 2006). Initial consonant sound / d / changes into (z) and (t) changes into /b/. Initial consonant sound / d / changes into (Z) and (t) changes into / b /. The Vowels sounds are also changed. For instance, (ai) is changed into (ar) and / ɪ / changes into /ʌ /.

5. Results and discussion

Table 4

PSM from pre-existent form	Incestuous PSM by semantic shifting	PSM Introducing a New form & Partial PSM	Total Entries
2	2	21	25
8%	8%	84%	100%

In the first form of PSM two items were selected from the data. It means 8 % words are added in Urdu from English pre-existent words. The frequency of the second form of PSM is the lowest as only 2 out of 25, 8% words are found in this category. The most occurring form of PSM is the third one in which 20/25, 84% words are categorized. The results show that the higher frequency is because of the higher productivity of this form of PSM. It means that Urdu language may receive more such PSM words with new form by adding partial PSM.

There are three items in this data set which are not documented in Urdu dictionary used for the purpose of the research. Hence 12 % words need to be documented in order to be a part of Urdu dictionary.

6. Conclusion

The results show an overall pattern of PSM in Urdu words. The selected data reveal that the most occurring PSM introducing the new form and partial PSM. This category is flexible as it allows the language users to articulate a foreign borrowed word using the native language's phonetic resources. 12% PSM vocabulary is not a part of the Urdu Dictionary. However, they are found in widely read Urdu newspapers. Zukermann's classification helps identifying the linguistic trends at corpus level, by a linguistic community. Another study can be conducted to know why these linguistic trends are prevalent in users of the Urdu language. For instance, why the most productive and frequent form is the third category of PSM. This could be answered by analyzing language attitude towards PSM words.

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